

MADANIY XABARDORLIKNI OSHIRISH VA EKOLOGIK BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH | xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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«Og‘ir ekologik sharoitga qaramasdan, mamlakatimiz taraqqiyotiga munosib hissa qo‘shib kelayotgan Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini, uning barcha shahar, tuman va ovullarini kompleks tarzda rivojlantirish, mehnatkash va matonatli, oqko‘ngil va bag‘rikeng qoraqalpoq elining hayotini obod va farovon etishga har qachongidan ham ustuvor ahamiyat qaratamiz.

Bizning oliy va ezgu maqsadimiz – birgalikdagi fidokorona mehnatimiz bilan Yangi O‘zbekiston tarkibida Yangi Qoraqalpog‘istonni bunyod etishdir.»

Sh.M.MIRZIYOYEV
O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti

Prezident: “Bu ko‘prik o‘zbek va qoraqalpoq xalqlari o‘rtasidagi og‘zibirlik va hamkorlik ko‘prigidir”.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini Xorazm viloyati bilan bog‘lovchi ko‘prik. Asosiy qo‘shma ko‘prikning uzunligi 413 metr bo‘lib, eni 8 metr; har bir oraliq‘i 66 metrni tashkil qiladi. Uning 7 ta ustuni 6 ta oraliqqa o‘rnatilgan.

KIRISH

2024-yilning 17–18-may kunlari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi Xo‘jayli tumanida o‘tkazilgan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy madaniy, etnografik va ekologik merosini keng jamoatchilikka tanitishda hamda turizm infratuzilmalarini mustahkamlashda muhim qadam bo‘ldi

Anjumanning asosiy maqsadi Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozoriga olib kirish va madaniy xabardorlikni oshirishdir. Qoraqalpog‘iston o‘zining tarixiy boyliklari, arxeologik yodgorliklari va o‘ziga xos tabiiy manzaralari bilan dunyo sayyohlarini jalb etadigan katta jozibadorlikka ega. Bu hududda jahon madaniy va tabiiy merosi obyektlariga mansub ko‘plab joylar mavjud bo‘lib, ularning aksariyati turizm infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishga asos bo‘ladi.

Xususan, Qoraqalpog‘istondagi insoniyat tamaddunidan hikoya qiluvchi arxeologik yodgorliklar bisyor. Hozirgi kunda Qoraqalpog‘istonda 300 dan ortiq arxeologik obyektlar mavjud bo‘lib, ulardan eng mashhurlari – Ko‘hna Urganch, Tupraqal‘a, Ellikqal‘a va Ayoqal‘a hududlaridagi qadimiy manzillardir. Bular, o‘z navbatida, sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirib, hududning turistik imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha muhokamalar o‘tkazildi. Birinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalariga bag‘ishlanib, mahalliy infratuzilmalarni takomillashtirish hamda turizm xizmatlarini kengaytirish bo‘yicha takliflar ishlab chiqildi. Ikkinchi yo‘nalishda etnografik turizmni rivojlantirish, xususan, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni targ‘ib etish va milliy madaniy boyliklarni namoyish qilish masalalari muhokama qilindi. Uchinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari orqali targ‘ib qilish masalalariga bag‘ishlandi.

Ushbu anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish yo‘lida muhim qadamdir. Turizm, madaniy meros va ekologik yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan taklif va tavsiyalar hududni xalqaro turistik xaritada o‘z o‘rniga ega bo‘lishiga yordam beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi tarixiy, madaniy va tabiiy boyliklarga ega hudud sifatida nafaqat O‘zbekiston, balki butun Markaziy Osiyoda alohida o‘rin tutadi. Bu hududni «ochiq osmon ostidagi arxeologik muzey» deb atash mumkin, chunki bu yerda qadimiy Xorazm madaniyatining markazi bo‘lgan Qoraqalpog‘istonda nafaqat arxeologik meros, balki etnografik va ekologik turizmni rivojlantirish uchun katta imkoniyatlar mavjud.

Qoraqalpog‘istonda o‘tkaziladigan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro anjuman ana

shunday salohiyatni namoyon etish va rivojlantirish maqsadida tashkil etilgan. Anjuman doirasida turli olimlar, tadqiqotchilar va xalqaro ekspertlar ishtirokida ekologik barqarorlik va madaniy merosni saqlash masalalari muhokama qilinib, zamonaviy turizm yo‘nalishlaridagi ilmiy-nazariy takliflar ishlab chiqildi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha quyidagi muhokamalar o‘tkazildi:

- *Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalari;*
- *Etnografik turizmni tashkil etishning asosiy xususiyatlari;*
- *Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida targ‘ib qilishning zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari.*

Anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida ekologik va etnografik turizm nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga tanitishga yordam berishi olgari surildi.

Anjumanda xalqaro institutlar vakillarining qatnashishi bejiz emas. Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy tarixi va Xorazm madaniyati bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan qadimiy yodgorliklar va arxeologik topinmalar bu hududni nafaqat tarixchilar, arxeologlar uchun, balki turistlar uchun ham jozibadorligini oshirib boradi.

Masalan, Ko‘kcha III qabristoni – qadimgi bronza davri madaniyatiga oid yodgorlik bo‘lib, millioddan avvalgi XIII-XI asrlarga oid, deb taxmin qilinadi. Bu madaniyatlar ko‘p asrlar davomida bir-biri bilan hamkorlikda yashaganini va turli etnik guruhlarning madaniy merosini o‘zida mujassam etganini ko‘rsatadi.

Masalan, S.P. Tolstov¹ tomonidan o‘rganilgan Tazabagyab madaniyatlari ham Qoraqalpog‘istonning arxeologik salohiyatining muhim qismi bo‘lib, ularni o‘rganish natijasida bronza davrining ikki madaniyati bir vaqtning o‘zida mavjud bo‘lgani ma‘lum bo‘lgan. Bu esa hududda turli tarixiy etnik va madaniy jarayonlar sodir bo‘lganidan dalolat beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘istonning ushbu yodgorliklari va arxeologik manzillari sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirishi mumkin.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasining turizm salohiyati juda katta bo‘lib, uni jahon turizm bozoriga zamonaviy marketing vositalari orqali chiqarish imkoni bor. Bu borada ekologik va etnografik turizm muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu turizm yo‘nalishlari nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki uning madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga yoyishda ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Mazkur anjuman, ayniqsa, Qoraqalpog‘istonning kelgusi turizm salohiyatini mustahkamlashda, asosiy yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan takliflarni keng tatbiq qilishda omil bo‘lib, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni rivojlantirish va yangi turizm xizmatlarini joriy qilishga, hudud aholisi uchun yetarli darajada doimiy va mavsumiy daromadli ish o‘rinlari yaratishga xizmat qiladi.

1 <https://ensiklopediya.uz>

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY
TA'LIM, FAN VA INNOVATSIYALAR
VAZIRLIGI

TOSHKENT DAVLAT
IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI

O'zbekiston Ekologik
partiyasi

QORAQALPOG'ISTON
RESPUBLIKASI TURIZM
BOSHQARMASI

QORAQALPOG'ISTON
RESPUBLIKASI XO'JAYLI
TUMANI HOKIMLIGI

TURIZM QO'MITASI MADANIY
ME'ROS OBYEKTлари MUAMMOLARINI
O'RGANISH VA TURUZMNI
RIVOJLANTIRISH
ILMIY-TADQIQOT INSITUTI

YANGI IQLIM INNOVATSIYALAR
MARKAZI

I-SHO'BA

Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalari

KARAKALPAKSTAN IS A REGION OF GREAT TOURISM OPPORTUNITIES!

Zarikeyev Rasul Polatovich

Deputy Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan for Tourism, Culture, Cultural Heritage, and Mass Communications.

The Republic of Karakalpakstan is part of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is located on the Turan Lowland. The Karakum desert is closely adjacent to it from the southwest, the Ustyurt plateau is located in the northwest, and the Kyzyl-Kum desert is in the northeast. In the northern part of the region, the territory of Karakalpakstan covers the southern part of the Aral Sea, on the dried bottom of which a new saline desert, the Aral-Kum, is now being formed.

The rich heritage of Karakalpakstan includes a culture and traditions that are different from other regions of Uzbekistan. The Republic has its own tourism potential among the frequently visited routes of the Great Silk Road in the field of ecological, ethnographic, cultural, historical, pilgrimage, archaeological and gastronomic tourism.

Annually, about 2 million tourists from the regions of Uzbekistan and about 200 thousand tourists from all over the world visit the Republic of Karakalpakstan. For domestic and international tourists there is a full range of tourism programs: from authentic, unknown travel destinations to extreme eco-excursions to the Aral Sea and the Ustyurt Plateau.

The territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is a kind of «archaeological reserve», numbering hundreds of archaeological sites. In the south of the republic there are ruins of castles of pre-Islamic civilization, historical and architectural complexes, sacred places that

open up interesting prospects for archaeological and pilgrimage tourism. In the center of Nukus there is the legendary Museum of Arts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan named after I.V. Savitsky, one of the largest museums in Uzbekistan, attracting tourists from all over the world with stunning works of art.

According to statistics, by May 2024, the Republic of Karakalpakstan was visited by 56.1 thousand foreign tourists. As part of the domestic tourism program, 468.2 thousand tourists traveled around the republic during the specified period of time. This indicates a growing flow of tourists to the republic and a good prospect for the development of the tourism sector in the region. To achieve this, infrastructure and services are being improved in Karakalpakstan. New flights are opening connecting the city of Nukus with the northern region of the republic - Muynak, and at the international level with the airports of Istanbul and Almaty.

To develop sustainable tourism in Karakalpakstan, infrastructure and services have been improved. Regular flights on the Nukus-Muynak-Nukus route have opened. Since June of this year, Nukus International Airport has been expanding its routes for guests from Istanbul and Almaty. Direct air connections with these countries will expand opportunities for promoting tourism potential in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Mobile communication and Internet services have been launched in the coastal area of the Aral Sea. More than a hundred tourist-class cars provide comfortable transportation of tourists around the region. The availability of accommodation for travelers in hotels is one of the important factors in tourism. Currently, there are 31 hotels, 27 hostels and 45 guest houses functioning in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

For international relations, marketing and promotion tourism potential a number of international festivals and cultural events have been organized since the beginning of this year.

The delegation of the Republic of Karakalpakstan took part in the international tourism fair «ITB Berlin 2024» in the capital of Germany with the aim of establishing international partnerships. Several travel agencies of the republic and the German Society for International Cooperation (GIZ) took part in it. Handouts on pilgrimage etiquette in Russian, Uzbek and English have been developed and distributed.

A multimedia exhibition «Savitsky's Diaries. Old and new» promoting culture and art from the collection of the State Museum of Arts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan named after Igor Savitsky was organized in the city of Tashkent.

The ethnographic festival «Navruz» was organized in the Muynak region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. It was attended by tourists from England,

Italy, France, Poland, Germany, Denmark, Thailand and other countries, as well as more than 20 investors from China, 30 media representatives and bloggers.

At the «Damir» hotel in Nukus the tourism fair called «Travel around Uzbekistan!» was organized for guests from all regions of Uzbekistan. More than 100 businessmen, artisans, media representatives and students took part in it. Participants were given flyers about the tourism potential of Karakalpakstan, its historical and cultural heritage sites.

As part of the «Tourism Week», an international scientific conference «Goodwill Ambassadors of the Aral Sea region», an exhibition «The Aral through the eyes of artists», an ecological marathon «Aral Eco Race», a gastronomic festival «99 types of fish dishes from the Aral Sea» and an exhibition of artisans were held in Nukus and the Muynak region.

At the initiative of the Tashkent State University of Economics, a youth festival «Mizdahkan - a sacred and mysterious place» was organized in the Khojeyly region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, with the participation of UN members, delegations from the USA, China, South Korea, Turkey, Ireland and the Bahamas. It is gratifying to say that for the first time in the history of

the republic, the guest of honor at the event was the participation of Nobel Prize laureate Mr. Rae Kwon Chung. Within the framework of the festival, an international scientific and practical conference: «Cultural education and the development of environmentally sustainable tourism» was held. Guests and participants of the festival visited a unique site for pilgrimage tourism - the ancient city of Mizdahkan.

The international youth festival «Taqiya» took place in the Khojeyly district - a spectacular display of national costumes from local fashion designers, in which all regions of Karakalpakstan, a number of regions of Uzbekistan and craftsmen from Turkmenistan participated.

The May program to promote tourism potential in the republic ends with a spectacular competition of fearless racers of sports cars, buggies and motorcycles - participants in the annual international extreme motorsport championship of Uzbekistan «Rally Muynak-2024». The extreme route run on the difficult route Muynak - the shore of the Aral Sea – Muynak, with a total length of 450 km. The winners of the motorsport competition were awarded by the event organizers.

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана
Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана
Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

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